

LEADCOR

LEADERSHIP DEVELOPMENT FOR OCCUPATIONAL
STRESS REDUCTION IN CORRECTIONAL SETTINGS

LEADCOR User's Manual

Leadership Competencies in Correctional Settings

Module IV – My Leadership Development Plan

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Project's website - <https://www.leadership-corrections.org/>

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Module IV – My Leadership Development Plan

Overview of the Module IV

Welcome to the **Module IV** about **My Leadership Development Plan!** This Module is divided into **1 Chapter**:

- In **Chapter “How to Develop a Leadership Plan?”**, we will focus on the subchapters:
 - What is a Leadership Development Plan?;
 - Steps of a Leadership Development Plan;
 - Build your own Leadership Development Plan.

By the end of this module, you will be able to:

- ◆ Understand what a Leadership Development Plan is
- ◆ Recognise the steps that require a Leadership Development Plan
- ◆ Comprehend how to build your individual Leadership Development Plan

Chapter 1 - How to Develop a Leadership Plan?

Sub-chapter 1.1 - What is a Leadership Development Plan?

How to be a Good Leader - What makes Leadership Effective? ¹

In order to ensure professional success, co-operation from employees, and greater efficiency, it is essential for a leader to fulfil some requirements. We discussed those requirements in the previous modules; however, we can summarise that an effective and authentic leader does not put her/himself before others. S/He is very humble, respectful, and altruistic.

The required aspects of effective leadership are as follows:

Figure 1. Required Aspects of Effective Leadership.

Leadership develops a person's personality and pushes them beyond their fundamental bounds, allowing them to perform at a higher level. It incorporates mental frameworks, personality traits, skills, and knowledge.

The following principles are what it takes to be a leader:

Figure 2. Principles of What it Takes to be a Leader

S/he would ensure that the employees had the necessary skills and abilities to accomplish the work successfully and efficiently. S/he would make sure that employees had no problem doing their attributed tasks.

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A competent leader would assess progress and provide constructive criticism on performance.

Leaders must be sympathetic and sensitive while focusing on people. They must value and respect their opinions and thoughts. They should listen to the employees with patience.

Finally, when an influential leader concentrates on the team, he/she should coordinate the group's activities. The leader should foster a sense of accomplishment and teamwork among his/her co-workers. The team's accomplishments should be celebrated, and the leader should assess and create a nice and sociable environment.

Leadership Development Plan ²

Leadership is a skill that develops with time. You may identify your developmental requirements and acquire a clear picture of the areas you need to improve by knowing more about yourself, your strengths and your shortcomings. Good leaders understand how to modify their behaviours, and they do it by increasing their self-awareness, which helps with behaviour modification.

Tailored leadership plans can be created to support an individual's personal and professional development. By boosting self-awareness and behaviour adjustment, customised plans can help you get to where you want to be in a specific time frame.

Behavioural changes might range from being a better listener to implementing one's attitude toward diversity. Leadership is a self-perpetuating cycle; this means that leadership is a circle that does not end, that one can only make constant improvements (at a very low or higher level).

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The **Leadership Development Plan** is a thorough strategy that assists you in establishing a strategic leadership path for your career. Your vision statement analyses your present condition and strategic strengths to identify where you want to be in the following 3-5 years. As a leader, you react more appropriately and effectively to various situations. **Create a Leadership Development Plan to improve your abilities to manage your learning by developing your self-awareness as a leader.** A good leadership plan should be well-documented and easily accessible. It should be adaptable to changing situations and adjustable.

Before commencing on a Leadership Development Plan, **you should ask yourself whether you are ready to commit to this type of endeavour.**

Determine what leadership abilities or competencies you already possess. Also, determine if you will be able to implement and stick to your goals over an extended period of time, preferably 8 to 24 months, to achieve the optimum outcomes.

Reflect on whether you have the patience and endurance to continue with the process despite setbacks. The process of leadership development is never-ending. Leadership development is a constant process that helps handle professional issues for everyone, regardless of how informed they are or equipped with the requisite competencies and abilities as a leader.

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Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 1.2 - Steps of a Leadership Development Plan

Steps to Develop a Leadership Plan ¹

You should collect the required information from your **self-assessment** before developing the plan so that you can aggregate and evaluate your findings. You may express the vision and create targets for Leadership development using this analysis.

Collecting Data and Data Analysis of the Self-Assessment

Determine which goals you want to improve over the following several years by reviewing the data you have gathered. There are five factors to consider:

Figure 3. Five Factors to Consider When Determining Which Goals Need Improvement.

Exemplification

This level entails a thorough examination of your present habits

Assessment

Decide on the methods you will use to measure your current skills and the approaches you will use to do so throughout the plan during the self-assessment process

Know-How

Determine whether you need to spend more time working with specific departments to overcome limitations and expand your knowledge in certain areas

Education

Determine which areas require further training or study

Articulating and realising the vision – setting of objectives ¹

The next stage considers your overall vision for your future. Create a personal vision and a strategy for where you want to be in the following three to five years.

It is not simple to put together a leadership development strategy. Every stage of the procedure necessitates a concerted effort and meticulous preparation. A Leadership Development Plan is created through a series of phases. The process begins with a self-assessment phase, after which the data gathered from self-assessments is utilised to define the vision and goals.

The next step is the formulation of SMART objectives, which contribute to enabling the objectives and identifying competencies that aid in the achievement of these objectives. Make a list of concrete goals you wish to attain to realise the vision. Goals should be **SMART** - **S**pecific, **M**easurable, **A**chievable, **R**ealistic and **T**ime-bound.

Figure 4. SMART Objectives.

Specific Objectives

Clearly and precisely state what goals you want to achieve over a specific timeline, as well as how and why you want to achieve them

Measurable Objectives

A Measurability criterion is essential since it aids in determining the areas of success and failure in achieving your goals

Achievable Objectives

A leader's goals should be realistic and achievable; otherwise, he/she may lose motivation

Realistic Objectives

A leader should have the appropriate resources and abilities to achieve those objectives, so the pre-defined targets should be achievable

Time-bound Objectives

Create a feeling of urgency and improve motivation by organising your goals around a specified time range or establishing deadlines

The following example can be considered **SMART objectives** for including in the leadership plan: **complete the E-Learning course on leadership competencies by the end of this month to achieve completion certification.**

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 1.3 - Build your own Leadership Development Plan

Writing the plan ¹

Setting developmental objectives in many competency areas is part of writing the plan. It is organised into three sections:

- Long-term objectives
- Responsibilities now and in the future
- Timeframes in which you wish to complete tasks.

Fill in your vision and sensible objectives based on your analysis; list your present duties and what you believe future ones will be. Create a timeframe for accomplishing your objectives and identify areas to improve your leadership character.

Common Elements to be included in a Leadership Development Plan ¹

1. Character Development: This is the main emphasis of leadership development, and it entails recognising and developing essential core competencies that contribute to the development of the character.

2. Example Setting and Leading: This entails laying out the behaviours that a leader would emulate. It is involved with determining what behaviours are desirable or practical.

3. Extension of Leadership Experience: It focuses on extending leadership experience through complex tasks, suitable leadership development training, and significant reading to keep current with best management practices and varied leadership styles.

The completion of a Leadership Development Plan follows the steps below (these essential elements are involved in the execution stage of a leadership plan):

- **Communicating the plan:** refers to exposing the growth plan to someone who can assist with self-improvement or leadership development.

- **Periodic monitoring of the progress:** This stage is primarily concerned with establishing a system that will allow you to assess performance regularly and make appropriate modifications as needed. Apart from continuous monitoring, recognising successes is also crucial as a leader moves through various stages of the growth plan to maintain motivation levels high.

Strategies for Leadership Development

1. Self-Assessment for Leadership Development: Newcomers can refine their strategies by completing personal assessments and developing personalised growth plans. Employee retention and motivation can be improved by including workers in career development programmes with mentorship and facilitation assistance.

2. Mentoring and coaching support for Developing Leadership Capabilities: Employee retention may be increased by having a well-planned mentorship program that provides thorough facilitation and assistance for developing the necessary skills and abilities. Mentors provide mentees with systematic and honest feedback on their work progress and areas for growth, as well as a corrective plan of action for growing their leadership ability.

3. Leadership Development Aligned with Technology: The complete leadership development process may be controlled efficiently from start to finish by deploying an integrated online software solution. Technology may be used to handle critical operations such as onboarding new employees, executing employee engagement and retention campaigns, mentoring and coaching for performance improvement, and thinking succession planning to replace essential leadership roles.

With these guidelines, now you are ready to **develop your Leadership Development Plan!** Go ahead and establish a strategic leadership path for your career.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

What did I learn?

- ◆ How to be a Good Leader - What makes Leadership Effective?
- ◆ Steps to Develop a Leadership Plan
- ◆ How to build your own Leadership Development Plan

References

Chapter 1 - How to Develop a Leadership Plan?

Sub-chapter 1.1 - What is a Leadership Development Plan?

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Sub-chapter 1.3 - Build your own Leadership Development Plan

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